

Additional file 9. Monosaccharide composition of non-cellulosic polymers determined by TMS (mol %) and cellulose content (%; w : w) in ball milled wood (BMW), LCC fractions and the residue in transgenic and wild type (WT) samples.

Fraction	Line	Ara	Rha	Fuc	Xyl	Man	MeGlcA	Gal	GalA	Glc	GlcA	Updegraff Cellulose
BMW	WT	2.91 ± 0.10	0.78 ± 0.02	0.61 ± 0.00	46.5 ± 1.4	3.69 ± 0.09	4.10 ± 0.11	2.00 ± 0.07	4.20 ± 0.17	34.0 ± 1.6	1.26 ± 0.08	17.7 ± 0.61
	TR	3.13 ± 0.11	0.74 ± 0.04	0.66 ± 0.04	44.1 ± 1.6	3.90 ± 0.10	3.95 ± 0.09	2.12 ± 0.14	4.09 ± 0.13	36.0 ± 1.5	1.35 ± 0.04	16.6 ± 1.68
LCC-X	WT	1.88 ± 0.07	2.57 ± 0.05	0.8 ± 0.09	47.0 ± 1.1	10.65 ± 0.32	2.03 ± 0.09	4.42 ± 0.12	5.86 ± 0.17	23.2 ± 0.3	1.55 ± 0.15	ND
	TR	2.08 ± 0.22	2.59 ± 0.07	0.75 ± 0.21	46.5 ± 0.8	10.47 ± 0.11	2.02 ± 0.18	4.84 ± 0.01*	6.97 ± 0.19*	22.2 ± 0.3*	1.53 ± 0.32	ND
LCC-1	WT	6.05 ± 0.35	5.72 ± 0.09	3.46 ± 0.43	13.5 ± 0.1	6.17 ± 0.18	3.69 ± 0.39	7.67 ± 0.31	42.14 ± 2.84	5.6 ± 0.3	6.00 ± 0.70	ND
	TR	5.61 ± 0.49	5.64 ± 0.16	2.78 ± 0.63	17.7 ± 0.9**	7.01 ± 0.48	3.29 ± 0.56	7.07 ± 0.62	40.34 ± 4.64	5.7 ± 0.4	4.90 ± 1.05	ND
LCC-2	WT	1.86 ± 0.18	1.88 ± 0.05	1.13 ± 0.15	59.6 ± 0.3	3.61 ± 0.03	2.95 ± 0.02	2.20 ± 0.13	5.86 ± 0.23	19.0 ± 0.2	1.93 ± 0.20	17.6 ± 0.97
	TR	2.07 ± 0.17	2.06 ± 0.07	1.25 ± 0.17	58.9 ± 1.9	4.03 ± 0.02**	3.09 ± 0.37	2.54 ± 0.15	6.02 ± 0.17	17.9 ± 1.2	2.10 ± 0.30	17.9 ± 1.75
LCC-3	WT	2.13 ± 0.32	2.28 ± 0.13	1.22 ± 0.36	63.1 ± 2.1	10.94 ± 0.09	3.67 ± 0.15	3.48 ± 0.33	7.14 ± 0.15	3.8 ± 0.1	2.29 ± 0.57	ND
	TR	2.12 ± 0.09	2.34 ± 0.03	1.12 ± 0.09	65.0 ± 0.3	10.25 ± 0.33*	3.78 ± 0.12	3.30 ± 0.07	6.59 ± 0.50	3.3 ± 0.1**	2.17 ± 0.13	ND
Residue	WT	1.49 ± 0.01	1.66 ± 0.03	0.93 ± 0.00	63.4 ± 2.2	2.47 ± 0.05	2.78 ± 0.20	1.86 ± 0.12	4.2 ± 0.14	19.5 ± 1.9	1.73 ± 0.04	31.0 ± 1.01
	TR	1.61 ± 0.08	1.66 ± 0.03	1.03 ± 0.10	60.7 ± 1.4	2.73 ± 0.06**	2.93 ± 0.11	2.02 ± 0.07	3.64 ± 0.10	21.8 ± 0.9**	1.90 ± 0.16	24.2 ± 0.15**

Mean ± SE, n = 3 technical replicates. WT is combination of 6 individual trees. TR is combination of two trees from each transgenic line (8, 4, 17). ND = not detected. Asterisks correspond to means significantly different from WT according to the ANOVA (* P ≤ 0.1, ** P ≤ 0.05, *** P ≤ 0.01, **** P ≤ 0.001).